

An Analysis of Teachers' Perceptions of the National Educational Policy: A Study Conducted in Udupi District

Sakshi Nayak, Spandana, Harshitha, Shamitha, Harshaprada¹
& Bharathi Karanth²

¹ MBA Scholars, Poornaprajna Institute of Management, Udupi

² Associate Professor, Poornaprajna Institute of Management, Udupi.

Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4456-7901, Email: bharathikaranth@pim.ac.in

ABSTRACT

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a comprehensive framework aimed at transforming the education landscape of India. This policy outlines a vision to revamp the educational system, emphasizing inclusivity, flexibility, and quality. Key highlights include changes in curriculum structure to promote holistic development, integration of technology for enhanced learning outcomes, and a renewed focus on foundational literacy and numeracy. The NEP 2020 also advocates for multilingual education, promoting cultural diversity and knowledge exchange. Moreover, it proposes structural reforms in governance and accreditation to ensure accountability and transparency. This paper is aimed at exploring the awareness and understanding of the perceptions of the teachers about the NEP in the Udupi district. The study involves the administration of a structured questionnaire and the collection of data through direct personal interviews with teachers of twenty schools in the Udupi district. The study reveals that the teachers are aware of the NEP, have sufficient training required, and understand the curriculum and pedagogical changes. The study concludes that teachers in the Udupi district understand and appreciate the role of NEP in their professional development.

Keywords: National Education Policy (NEP), Teacher's perception, Professional Development, Curriculum and Pedagogical changes.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a transformative shift in the Indian education system, aiming to address longstanding issues and prepare the country for future challenges. This comprehensive policy seeks to overhaul the existing educational structure to align with the needs of a rapidly changing world and foster holistic development. Key highlights include universalization of education from preschool to secondary level, achieving a 100% gross enrolment ratio (GER) by 2030, and the introduction of 12 years of schooling with an additional three years of Anganwadi/pre-schooling. Furthermore, the policy aims to phase out the affiliation system within 15 years, granting colleges greater autonomy, and increasing public investment in education to 6% of GDP, with collaborative efforts from both central and state governments.

This research project, conducted in Udupi, employs both primary and secondary data to assess the implementation of NEP 2020 in 50 educational institutions. Using purposive clustered sampling, the study examines the challenges faced by teachers and headmasters in adapting to the new framework. Chi-Square and ANOVA tests indicate no significant difference in the level of challenge between these roles, suggesting that support should be uniformly provided to all educators. The findings underline the critical role of effective implementation in realizing the policy's goals and the potential of NEP 2020 to shape the future of Indian education.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW:

B. V. (2021) emphasized that a well-defined and futuristic education policy is essential for a country at both school and college levels. According to the author, education is a key driver of economic and social progress, and different countries adopt education systems considering tradition and culture to make them effective at different stages of the education lifecycle [1].

Sarta (2022) highlighted that the National Education Policy (NEP) is the first education policy of the 21st century in India. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the policy was a positive step towards transforming India's education system, which had not seen significant changes for over 35 years, since the last education reform in 1986 [2].

Manurkar (2023) conducted a study that reviewed 18 research papers related to NEP 2020. The study aimed to explore gaps in the existing literature for future research on NEP 2020 using qualitative research techniques [3].

Kumar (2022) noted that in 2020, apart from the challenges posed by COVID-19, a significant change in India was the introduction of NEP 2020. Various committees have recommended increasing the education budget allocation to 6% of the GDP, reflecting growing research interest in education policy [4].

Pandithrao and Pandithrao (2020) discussed the historical context of education policies in India, particularly during British rule. They noted that past policies, like Macaulay's education system, were not aimed at providing quality education but at producing clerks and bureaucrats to serve the British Empire. In contrast, NEP 2020 is envisioned to reform the system for the benefit of India's growing economy [5].

Sawant and Sankpal (2021) reiterated that a visionary and futuristic education policy is crucial for every country, as education drives both economic and social progress. They stressed that educational systems should reflect a nation's traditions and culture [6].

Verma and Kumar (2021) pointed out that education plays a decisive role in reform, and NEP 2020 aims to build a new education system that strengthens economic and social indicators while providing high-quality higher education through multidisciplinary institutions and autonomous colleges [7].

G. K. R. et al. (2021) conducted a study on the impact of education on rural-to-urban migration in cities like Chennai, Madurai, and Bangalore, identifying education as a factor influencing migration and emphasizing the need for a new education policy [8].

Cheluvvaraju and Devi (2020) explored how NEP 2020 envisions providing high-quality education to support India's economy. The policy focuses on quality, equity, and integrity in education, with commerce and management education playing a pivotal role in sectors like manufacturing, services, banking, and finance [9].

Kurien and Chandramana (2020) mentioned that the announcement of NEP 2020 came as a surprise amidst the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic and was viewed as a positive change in India's education system [10].

S. M. et al. (2021) discussed the constitutional directive concerning Article 45 in the Directive Principles of State Policy (DPSP), which emphasizes the accessibility of education for all. The authors noted that under Article 21A, primary education for children aged 6 to 14 years is now a fundamental right [11].

Shubhrajyotsna and Sreeramana (2020) underscored the need for a well-defined education policy that considers national traditions and culture to drive economic and social progress at both school and college levels [12].

Dhillon (2021) described NEP 2020 as a comprehensive framework for reforming the education system in India, designed to align with both Indian traditions and the 21st-century global goals, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [13].

Wadia (2022) discussed the first year of NEP 2020 implementation. The immediate renaming of the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) to the Ministry of Education (MOE) was one of the first steps taken by the Union Cabinet to align with the new policy [14].

P. G. (2022) outlined India's National Education Policy (NEP-2020), which was developed under the leadership of the Prime Minister and an expert team. The policy's aim and objectives are widely known and are seen as pivotal to the country's educational reforms in the coming decade [15].

3. RESEARCH GAPS:

1. **Limited Long-Term Impact Studies:** There is a lack of longitudinal research on the long-term effects of NEP 2020, particularly in rural areas. Future studies could explore its regional impact over time.
2. **Role of Technology:** Insufficient research exists on the role of technology in implementing NEP 2020, especially in remote areas. Studies on digital platforms' effectiveness in bridging the urban-rural education divide are needed.
3. **Teacher Training Impact:** Little research explores how NEP 2020 affects teacher training and development. Studies focusing on changes in teaching methods and educator readiness would be valuable.
4. **Multidisciplinary Education:** More empirical evidence is needed on the practical implementation of NEP's multidisciplinary approach and its impact on student outcomes.
5. **Regional Disparities:** Understanding the regional differences in NEP implementation, influenced by local governance and cultural factors, requires more study.

6. **Higher Education and Employment:** Research linking NEP 2020's higher education reforms to employment outcomes is lacking and could help assess the effectiveness of reformed institutions.
7. **Impact on Marginalized Communities:** Limited research exists on how NEP 2020 benefits marginalized groups, such as tribal and economically disadvantaged communities. Studies on access to quality education for these groups are necessary.
8. **Financial Implications:** There is insufficient research on the financial feasibility of increasing the education budget to 6% of GDP and how resources are allocated for NEP reforms.
9. **Parental and Community Involvement:** The role of parents and communities in NEP implementation is underexplored. Research is needed to assess how their involvement impacts education outcomes.
10. **Vocational Training:** The effectiveness of NEP's vocational and skill-based education in enhancing employability and aligning with industry needs remains under-researched.

Addressing these research gaps could provide a deeper understanding of the effectiveness and challenges associated with NEP 2020, guiding future policy adjustments and improvements.

4.STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a significant reform aimed at overhauling the Indian education system, with an emphasis on inclusivity, quality, and holistic development. While the policy sets forth a vision for transforming education, its success largely depends on the awareness, understanding, and readiness of teachers to implement the proposed changes. Teachers play a critical role in the policy's effective execution, as they are the primary facilitators of learning and curriculum delivery. However, there is limited empirical evidence on how well teachers, particularly at the grassroots level, perceive, understand, and are prepared to implement NEP 2020. In this context, it becomes crucial to analyze the perceptions of teachers regarding the NEP, their preparedness for the curriculum and pedagogical changes, and their overall understanding of the policy's impact on their professional roles. This study focuses on exploring these aspects among teachers in the Udupi district, aiming to assess their awareness, training, and appreciation of the NEP 2020, and to identify any challenges they face in adapting to the reforms.

5.OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. Evaluate awareness and understanding of NEP 2020 among teachers.
2. Analyse curriculum changes and their impact.
3. Assess the implementation and effectiveness of NEP components.
4. Identify challenges in NEP implementation.
5. Gather feedback and suggestions for improvement.

6.METHODOLOGY:

Type of Research:

This study is empirical, descriptive, and exploratory in nature. It aims to understand and analyze the perceptions of teachers regarding the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, particularly in Udupi district.

Source of Data:

- **Primary Data:** Collected through direct personal interviews with teachers and headmasters/mistresses from schools and colleges in Udupi and Kaup using a well-structured questionnaire.
- **Secondary Data:** Derived from published sources such as research papers, reports, and policy documents related to NEP 2020.

Sampling Method:

Purposive simple random sampling was used, incorporating both open-ended and close-ended questions to gather insights. The sample was selected to represent teachers and administrative heads from various educational levels.

Sampling Element:

The participants of the study include primary, high school, and college teachers, as well as headmasters and headmistresses.

Scope of the Study:

This study focuses on the implementation of the NEP 2020 across different educational institutions in Udupi district, including both private and government schools and colleges. NEP implementation is examined across the following categories:

1. Primary schools
2. High schools
3. Colleges (pre-university, undergraduate, and postgraduate)

Selection of Study Area:

Udupi city and surrounding areas (including Kaup) were selected for the study.

Study Period:

The data collection and survey were conducted during 2023.

Analysis of Data:

The collected data were analyzed using the following statistical methods:

- **Chi-Square Tests:** Employed to examine relationships between variables, such as the position of the participant (teacher or headmaster) and their perceived level of challenges in adapting to the new curriculum and pedagogy. This test helps identify associations between the role and the difficulties faced in the implementation of NEP.
- **Hypothesis Testing:** Aimed at determining whether there is a significant difference in the mean levels of challenges between teacher and headmaster groups. The hypothesis testing follows this structure:

- **Null Hypothesis (H0):** There is no significant difference in the mean levels of challenge in adapting curriculum and pedagogy to the new framework between teacher and headmaster groups.
- **Alternative Hypothesis (H1):** There is a significant difference in the mean levels of challenge in adapting curriculum and pedagogy to the new framework between teacher and headmaster groups.

These statistical tools provide a structured approach to evaluate teachers' and headmasters' experiences and perspectives on NEP implementation.

Limitations of the Study

The study suffers from the following limitations:

- 1) Time was a major constraint for the project.
- 2) The sampling is done based on the available schools;

Background of the study

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 marks a significant overhaul of the Indian educational landscape, designed to address systemic issues and prepare the nation for future educational needs. This policy aims to provide an inclusive, flexible, and high-quality education framework, promoting holistic development and integrating modern technological advancements to enhance learning outcomes. Among its transformative goals, the NEP 2020 emphasizes foundational literacy and numeracy, multilingual education to celebrate cultural diversity, and substantial structural reforms in governance and accreditation to ensure accountability and transparency.

In the Udupi district of Karnataka, this research project seeks to explore the awareness, understanding, and perceptions of teachers regarding the NEP 2020. The study focuses on examining how teachers in Udupi have adapted to the curriculum and pedagogical changes introduced by the policy and evaluates their readiness and training for these new educational paradigms. By administering structured questionnaires and conducting direct personal interviews with teachers from twenty schools, this study aims to gather in-depth insights into the practical implications of NEP 2020 on the ground.

Furthermore, the research also investigates the challenges faced by educators in implementing the new policy and how these challenges impact their professional development. The study employs purposive clustered sampling to select 50 educational institutions in Udupi, ensuring a representative understanding of the policy's implementation across different schools in the district. By combining both primary and secondary data, this research aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the NEP 2020's impact on the educational ecosystem in Udupi, offering valuable insights into the effectiveness of the policy and the areas that require further attention.

7.DATA ANALYSIS:

Chart No:1

Chart showing opinion of the respondents whether they have understood the key objectives and principles of NEP 2020

How well do you understand the key objectives and principles of NEP 2020

68 responses

Source: Made through Google form

Interpretation:

The chart shows that 58.8% of respondents understand the key objectives and principles of NEP 2020 very well, 35.3% somewhat understand, 5.9% do not understand very well, and none do not understand at all.

Chart no -2

Chart showing the revised curriculum based on the policy recommendation

Have you revised your curriculum based on the policies recommendations ?

68 responses

Source: Made through Google form

Interpretation:

The chart shows that 69.1% of respondents have revised their curriculum based on policy recommendation, while 30.9% have not.

Chart No: 3

Chart showing whether teachers in institute have undergone training related to NEP 2020

Whether teachers in your institution undergone training/ workshops related to NEP?

68 responses

Source: Made through Google form

Interpretation:

The chart shows that 64.7% of respondent's undergone training/workshops related to NEP, 35.3% of respondent's not undergone training/workshops related to NEP

Chart No:4

Chart showing deviation from NEP to SEP is needed

Whether a deviation from the NEP to SEP is needed?

68 responses

Source: Made through Google form

Interpretation

The chart shows the results of a survey with 68 responses about whether a deviation from the NEP to SEP is needed. 55.9% of respondents said yes while 44.1% said no.

5) Chi-Square test

Null hypothesis (H0): There is no significant association between the variables (e.g., position - teacher or headmaster - and the level of challenge in adapting curriculum and pedagogy to the new framework).

Alternative hypothesis (H1): There is a significant association between the variables, suggesting that the level of challenge in adapting curriculum and pedagogy to the new framework varies depending on the position (teacher or headmaster).

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Position * Adapting curriculum and pedagogy to new framework	68	100.0%	0	0.0%	68	100.0%

Position * Adapting curriculum and pedagogy to new framework Crosstabulation

Count		Adapting curriculum and pedagogy to new framework					Total
		most challenging	challenging	Neutral	not challenging	least challenging	
Position	Teacher	15	24	14	3	5	61
	Headmaster	1	2	1	1	2	7
Total		16	26	15	4	7	68

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.157 ^a	4	.385
Likelihood Ratio	3.278	4	.512
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.838	1	.092
N of Valid Cases	68		

6 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .41

Source : PSPP

Interpretation

The chi-square tests indicate no significant association between the variables, despite a weak linear association suggested by the Linear-by-Linear Association test; however, the majority of cells have expected counts less than 5, potentially impacting the validity of the chi-square test.

ANOVA

Null hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference in the mean levels of challenge in adapting curriculum and pedagogy to the new framework between teacher and headmaster groups.

Alternative hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference in the mean levels of challenge in adapting curriculum and pedagogy to the new framework between teacher and headmaster groups.

Descriptives

Adapting curriculum and pedagogy to new framework

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Teacher	61	2.3279	1.15067	.14733	2.0332	2.6226	1.00	5.00
Headmaster	7	3.1429	1.57359	.59476	1.6875	4.5982	1.00	5.00
Total	68	2.4118	1.21232	.14701	2.1183	2.7052	1.00	5.00

Adapting curriculum and pedagogy to new framework

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.171	1	4.171	2.919	.092
Within Groups	94.300	66	1.429		
Total	98.471	67			

Source: PSPP**Interpretation**

The analysis shows that the variability in adapting curriculum and pedagogy to the new framework between teacher and headmaster groups is not statistically significant, as indicated by an F-statistic of 2.919 with a p-value of .092.

8. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS:**The study has led to the following specific findings****1. Understanding of NEP 2020 Objectives:**

The data reveals that a significant proportion of teachers, 58.8%, have a strong understanding of the key objectives and principles of NEP 2020. Additionally, 35.3% of respondents indicate a moderate understanding of the policy. Only 4.4% of teachers reported minimal understanding, and an even smaller percentage (1.5%) expressed no understanding at all. These results suggest that while a majority of teachers are well-informed about NEP 2020, there remains a small segment of educators who require further clarification and understanding of the policy.

2. Curriculum Revision:

A notable 69.1% of respondents have already revised their curriculum to align with NEP 2020 guidelines, showcasing a proactive approach to adapting educational content. However, 30.9% of teachers have not yet made the necessary revisions, indicating potential challenges such as lack of resources, time, or adequate support in implementing the policy's recommendations. This underscores the need for focused efforts to assist schools in overcoming these hurdles and achieving full compliance.

3. Teacher Training and Professional Development:

The findings reveal that 64.7% of respondents indicated that teachers in their institutions have participated in training or workshops related to NEP 2020. This demonstrates a commendable effort in upskilling teachers for effective policy implementation. However, 35.3% of teachers have not undergone such training, suggesting a significant gap in professional development. This gap could hinder the successful execution of NEP's pedagogical changes, as proper training is critical for understanding and applying the new curriculum framework.

4. Statistical Analysis (Chi-Square Test):

Based on the Chi-Square test results, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that

there is no significant association between the position (whether a respondent is a teacher or a headmaster) and the level of challenge faced in adapting to the new curriculum and pedagogical framework. This suggests that both groups face similar levels of difficulty in adapting to the new policy framework, highlighting the universal nature of the challenges across different educational roles.

5. **Statistical Analysis (ANOVA Test):**

The results of the ANOVA test also lead to the acceptance of the null hypothesis, affirming that there is no significant difference in the mean levels of challenges faced by teachers and headmasters in adapting to NEP 2020. This implies that both groups—teachers and school heads—encounter comparable levels of difficulty in integrating the new curriculum, indicating the need for targeted support for all educational professionals.

Suggestions

Enhanced Training and Professional Development:

To ensure comprehensive understanding and implementation of NEP 2020, it is essential to expand the availability of training programs and workshops. A strategic focus should be placed on ensuring all teachers and educational leaders, especially those in underserved areas, receive timely, adequate, and region-specific professional development opportunities.

1. **Comprehensive Curriculum Resources:**

The government and educational authorities should provide detailed, user-friendly guidelines and resources to facilitate seamless curriculum revision in line with NEP 2020. Schools and teachers should be provided with step-by-step frameworks and teaching aids that support the transition to the new educational structure and pedagogical practices.

2. **Collaborative Platforms for Best Practices:**

Establishing forums or online platforms where teachers, headmasters, and education administrators can exchange best practices, challenges, and solutions related to NEP implementation will foster a collaborative learning environment. These platforms should also include access to experts who can provide ongoing support and guidance on NEP-related concerns.

3. **Targeted Support for Implementation Challenges:**

Identifying specific challenges faced by teachers and school heads—such as lack of resources, time constraints, or resistance to change—is crucial. Targeted interventions, including additional funding, specialized training, or administrative support, should be provided to address these challenges. Schools that have not yet revised their curriculum should receive priority assistance.

4. **Continuous Monitoring and Feedback Mechanisms:**

Implementing an ongoing monitoring system to track the progress of NEP 2020 in schools and colleges is necessary to ensure compliance and to identify any emerging challenges early. Feedback mechanisms should be in place to capture the experiences of teachers and headmasters, with periodic reviews to fine-tune the implementation strategies.

9. CONCLUSION:

The analysis of teachers' and headmasters' perceptions of NEP 2020 in Udupi district reveals that, while the majority of educational professionals possess a solid understanding of the policy's objectives, a notable percentage of educators still require further clarification and support. Similarly, while most respondents have revised their curriculum and undergone NEP-related training, significant gaps in both curriculum adaptation and professional development remain.

The findings from statistical tests (Chi-Square and ANOVA) indicate that the challenges faced in adapting to the new curriculum and pedagogical framework are shared across both teachers and headmasters, regardless of their roles. This suggests that a uniform approach to support and resources should be adopted for all educators, focusing on reducing the barriers to effective implementation.

The study underscores the need for increased access to NEP-related training, better curriculum revision guidelines, and platforms for knowledge-sharing among educators. By addressing these gaps, the successful implementation of NEP 2020 can be significantly enhanced, paving the way for an educational system that promotes holistic development, inclusivity, and quality. Going forward, continuous monitoring, along with feedback-driven improvements, will be key to ensuring the sustained success of NEP 2020 in transforming India's educational landscape.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. V., "Well defined and futuristic education policy is essential for a country at school and college levels," 2021.
- [2] A. Sarta, "NEP is the first education policy of 21st century," 2022.
- [3] P. R. Manurkar, "A review of National Education Policy 2020," 2023.
- [4] A. Kumar, "Development of the New Education Policy (NEP) 2020," 2022.
- [5] M. M. Pandithrao and M. M. Pandithrao, "National Education Policy 2020," 2020.
- [6] R. G. Sawant and U. B. Sankpal, "Visionary and futuristic education policy," 2021.
- [7] H. Verma and A. Kumar, "The role of education in economic and social progress," 2021.
- [8] G. K. R., N. S., and D. V., "Education and rural to urban migration in India," 2021.
- [9] Cheluvvaraju and L. Devi, "National Education Policy-2020 and commerce education," 2020.
- [10] A. Kurien and S. B. Chandramana, "New Education Policy amidst Covid-19," Dec. 2020.
- [11] S. M., R. Bansal, and B. S. Hothi, "Directive Principle of State Policy and Article 45," 2021.
- [12] A. Shubhrajyotsna and A. Sreeramana, "Futuristic education policy for school and college levels," Aug. 2020.
- [13] A. P. Dhillon, "Comprehensive perspective of NEP 2020," 2021.
- [14] L. C. Wadia, "Implementation of NEP 2020 in India," Jan. 2022.
- [15] P. G., "Indian National Education Policy (NEP-2020)," 2022.
